

ADVANTAGES OF USING INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10205373>

Abstract: Education, which has become a topical issue not only in our country, but also in other countries, and with it the issues of components related to the periodic structure of education in the pedagogical process and in accordance with the main features of educational technology and teacher training on the basis of this periodicity The issues of determining the structure are discussed

Keywords: education, society, research methods, social significance, holistic view, teaching methods, student, worldview, interdisciplinary communication, innovative technology, didactic system, pedagogical support, innovative school.

The educational process is continuous, based on the principle of sequence and consistency, and is effective. From the earliest times to the present day, "Human education" as an urgent issue requires equal consideration in all peoples of the earth. Honorable President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev said, "The main goal of building an independent and strong state in Uzbekistan is to build a fair society where people, their rights and freedoms are considered the highest value and respected. At the same time, it is to further strengthen our rightful place in the Muslim world and the world community. First of all, we understand that this is in line with improving the system of education and enlightenment, directing the youth who are the future of our country to receive modern knowledge, and raising a well-rounded person. In particular, Martin Jay expresses the following opinion about the continuous continuation of education in pedagogical processes and its periodicity: "We can say that the periodic structure of education in the pedagogical process is the sum of its components in accordance with the main characteristics of education technologies. In the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, the following thoughts are given about "Education". "Tarbiya" is derived from the Arabic word, which means "to develop", "to take care of", "to teach", "to impart knowledge". Education is a practical pedagogical process aimed at forming certain physical, mental, moral and spiritual qualities in a person; a set of measures taken to ensure that a person has the characteristics necessary for

living in society. Education is the most ancient and eternal value that ensures the humanity of a person.

Neither an individual nor a human society can exist without education. Because the values that ensure the existence of a person and society are passed from one generation to another only because of education.[2] In addition, it is also interpreted as education, morals, etc. Thus, in pedagogy, there are several concepts of the "education" category at the same time. One of the most common concepts is the understanding of education as a specially organized process of imparting the most important experiences of education to the learning generation. Based on this, it is correct to conclude that teaching is the basis of any educational process. The social qualities of a person with poor moral education begin to shine. A person with good moral education looks for the right ways to satisfy his needs and communicates with people, improving his good social qualities. Education is a continuous process that goes on for centuries. In this case, the state of increase and exaggeration is visible at all times. The philosophical aspect of the consideration of the education system implies the justification of the content and goals of education, its clarification and the connection with the desired content of education. As mentioned above, there are different opposing approaches in the education system under today's views. Education is based on socially determined and purposeful influence on the child's personality. Education is carried out in a certain form and through certain methods. A different approach to education is related to the creation of a humanitarian educational system. This approach, first of all, occurs with the above-mentioned process of individualization. It should be related to the goal of the child mastering the issues of socialization as well as possible. Let's remember once again that individualization is the activity of adults and the child to maintain and develop the unique individuality that the child has in his individual experience, according to our thinking.

Education means a set of all influences, activities, actions, aspirations aimed at forming a human personality, ensuring his active participation in social, political, cultural and educational life. Education is not only the processes carried out in the family, school, children and youth organizations, but also includes the ideology instilled in its leading ideas through mass media, newspapers and magazines. Because education is a broader concept than education. Of course, education is a product of consciousness, but at the same time it is an important factor that determines the level of consciousness and its development, that is, it forms and enriches the spirituality of the people. Therefore, it is impossible to

develop spirituality without changing the education system and, on this basis, consciousness. It is known that school is very important in the process of educating the young generation. Education of students is carried out together with their education. But education has its own task, content, methods and means of implementation. The integrity of the learning and education process is one of the most important pedagogical tasks for educational institutions. Therefore, educational activities outside the classroom and school are directly related to the educational process. Educational activities become the basis of healthy life, healthy lifestyle, healthy faith, perfection. In the context of raising a perfect generation, factors such as loyalty to national values, a conscious attitude to maintaining peace and tranquility in society, creating a peaceful and prosperous life, striving to raise social spirituality occupy a key place in educational work. It is necessary to form the political consciousness of young people, to have a conscious attitude to the environment and society, to love the Motherland with unlimited loyalty, to cherish the national values of our people - this should be the core of patriotic education.

The development of the human personality is a very complex and continuous process. Parents, school, neighborhood, friends, public organizations, environment, mass media, art, literature, nature, etc. directly influence his education. In creating all the above life experiences, it is very important to educate a person through the sphere of influence of mutual cooperation and to protect him from the environment that negatively affects his formation as a person, while ensuring the unity of education. The main goal of education is to develop and implement effective organizational and pedagogical forms and tools based on the rich national, spiritual and historical traditions, customs and universal values of the people in the spiritual and moral education of the young generation.[3] The main task of education is the mental, moral, free-thinking and physical development of a person, as well as creating ample opportunities for the comprehensive development of his abilities. The real basis of education is the following

- To prepare young people to think freely, to help them understand the meaning of life, to form their ability to manage and control themselves, to have a purposeful approach to their personal life, to awaken in them a sense of unity of plan and action;
- Identifying the knowledge and creative potential of every teenager and developing them. Preparation of conditions for directing human activity in

various fields, bringing out children's creativity and talent and further supporting them;

-Educational tools such as the formation of standards of humanitarian etiquette (understanding each other), manners of behavior should be widely used.

According to the results of influencing the students, the methods can be divided into two groups:

-Ethical standards, affecting the creation of motives, the formation of imagination, concepts, ideas;

- Affecting the formation of habits that determine one or another type of behavior [4]

At present, more objective and convenient methods are used that reflect the single goal, content and orderliness of educational methods. Therefore, education is always in accordance with the level of development of productive forces and the type of social relations characteristic of a certain socio-historical formation. The state implements its policy through education, that is, it forms a person who responds to its ideology, ethics and policy, and prepares the personnel it needs. Education is required by the demands of society, and as labor tools and tools develop and improve, new types and forms of labor activity, distribution of labor products appear, and as relations between labor participants change, education also changes.[5] Education of the young generation is a national task. In addition to the institutions that are invited to directly engage in educational work in our republic, educational institutions, vocational and technical educational institutions, secondary special and higher educational institutions, also people of various professions participate in this important work. Therefore, studying the science of human education and its laws - pedagogy - is an important task of those who are related to it. Education and upbringing cannot be separated from each other, these two processes are harmonious, organized on a continuous basis only when they are polite, have moral qualities, high spirituality, and at the same time are knowledgeable, intelligent, mentally and physically healthy. It educates patriotic young people who have a broad worldview and thinking, who are the owners of modern professions.

In addition to the fact that eastern thinkers made an invaluable contribution to the development of world science in the teaching of the science of "education", in their activities they glorified man, philanthropy, justice, nobility, friendship, honesty, hard work, humility, generosity. , inculcating the ideas he put forward about courage, kindness, manners, morals, knowledge and enlightenment is of

great educational value: studying the legacy of our great thinkers in the "Education" classes has an incomparable educational and educational value.

After all, it would be appropriate if young people, who enter the hearts and minds of young people as a light and make a worthy contribution to the prosperity of our Motherland Uzbekistan as a blessed country, should study more carefully the rich heritage created by our great ancestors.

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